

DEVELOPMENT AND ACCEPTABILITY OF A MULTI-PURPOSE DRAFTING TABLE

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ABSTRACT

This research project aimed to develop and evaluate the acceptability of a multi-purpose drafting table. The Project Development Method (PDM) was employed to conceptualize the design and specifications, followed by construction and assembly. A descriptive-evaluative research design was utilized to evaluate the table's design, construction, functionality, comfort, durability, safety, and instructional applicability. Data was collected through questionnaires, interviews, and observations from industry experts, TVE teachers, and senior/junior drafting students. The results indicated that the multi-purpose drafting table received high acceptability ratings across all criteria, deemed "very good" in design and construction, "very functional," "very comfortable," "very durable," and "very safe." ANOVA analysis revealed significant differences in the evaluations of the three groups of respondents regarding functionality, comfort, durability, and safety, highlighting varying needs and preferences. The study concludes that the multi-purpose drafting table is a highly accepted project with potential for mass production and income generation. Recommendations include incorporating more features, utilizing high-quality materials, and exploring unique designs to enhance its overall functionality and user experience.

Keywords: *Multi-purpose Drafting Table, Instructional Applicability, Project Development Method, Industry Experts, Functionality*

INTRODUCTION

The primary objective of the teaching and learning process is to facilitate significant behavioral changes through active participation and critical thinking of the learner. This transformation is heavily dependent on the availability and proper use of school facilities, equipment, and other necessary resources (Turano, 2005). For classroom instruction to be effective, the classroom environment, particularly its physical aspects including fixtures and facilities, must enable students to perform at their highest potential (Landau, 2004; Stewart et al., 1997).

The physical environment is the foundation for creating an orderly setting conducive to learning (Stewart et al., 1997). Crafting this environment involves selecting and arranging furniture, organizing seating to facilitate learning, and ensuring materials, tools, and areas are accessible. Studies have shown that the classroom's physical environment directly impacts teachers' and students' behavior and thought processes (Marzano & Marzano, 2003).

Furniture plays a crucial role in the physical environment, shaping traffic patterns and ensuring materials are easily accessible to students (Landau, 2004). Proper furniture arrangement can foster a cooperative working environment, enhancing student interactions and allowing activities to proceed without interruption (Stewart et al., 1997). School facilities, including equipment, furniture, and instructional materials, are pivotal for the smooth operation of the teaching and learning process. They enable teachers to accomplish their tasks effectively and help students learn and achieve their fullest potential (Marzano & Marzano, 2003).

However, many schools in the Philippines face a shortage of instructional equipment and materials. In Technical Vocational Schools, for instance, shop work is challenging for both students and teachers due to a lack of materials and equipment (Salandan, 2008). In Drafting shops, students struggle with their drawing tables. Maintaining a clean, smooth surface for drawing, painting, and other exercises is crucial, but existing tables are often worn out and gritty (Ramos, 2010).

Moreover, students frequently need to move to different rooms for AutoCAD drawing, which is stressful and time-consuming. The lack of ventilation in these areas further adds to the discomfort (Torres, 2012). This highlights the need for an innovative solution: the "Multi-Purpose Drafting Table." This table addresses these issues and offers versatility for various tasks such as drawing, sketching, cutting, tracing, painting, writing, silk screening, T-shirt printing, and architectural drawing using Computer-Aided Design (CAD).

The proposed Multi-Purpose Drafting Table features a transparent tempered glass surface for smoothness and easy cleaning, an adjustable top that can incline between 15 to 80 degrees, a built-in computer set, an electric fan, a clip table lamp, and a fluorescent tube for silk screening. It is also movable for easy transfer. This table is particularly

beneficial for Drafting students in Technical Vocational schools, as well as for home and office use, providing a comfortable workspace (Fernandez, 2015).

This project exemplifies Filipino inventiveness in constructing and innovating a multi-purpose drafting table suitable for Drafting, CAD, and Technical Drawing. It fosters a partnership between the academe and draftsmen, aiming to create high-quality devices for classroom instruction and laboratory classes. Administrators and curriculum planners should recognize vocational and technical programs that meet societal demands for CAD expertise (Garcia, 2013). Strengthening the relationship between industry and academe is crucial for economic development (Pascua, 2018).

This study encourages innovation for teachers in creating homemade multipurpose equipment for shops and laboratory sessions. This project can also serve as baseline data for future researchers in their inventive endeavors (Santos, 2016).

Given these potential benefits, this study aims to develop, design, and evaluate a multi-purpose drafting table.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this research study was to design, construct, and evaluate the acceptability of a *Multi-purpose Drafting Table* to help address the problem of inadequate instructional tools and equipment at Reina Mercedes Vocational and Industrial School, specifically in Drafting Technology.

Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the process involved in the design and construction of the proposed Multi-purpose Drafting Table?
2. What is the level of acceptability of the Multi-purpose Drafting Table as evaluated by Industry Experts, Technical Vocational Education (TVE) Teachers, and Senior and Junior Drafting students, in terms of:
 - a. Design and construction;
 - b. Functionality;
 - c. Comfort;
 - d. Durability;
 - e. Safety; and
 - f. Instructional applicability?
3. Is there a significant difference in the evaluation of the three groups of respondents as to the acceptability of the Multi-purpose Drafting Table?
4. What further improvements can be made to the developed Multi-purpose Drafting Table?

METHODOLOGY

Method of Research Used

This research used the Project Development Method (PDM) whereby the design and specifications of the Multi-purpose Drafting Table were conceptualized. PDM aims to give students theoretical and practical knowledge on how to make projects by following appropriate steps in consonance with the research development process, i.e., from the research design to the research finalization.

The multi-purpose drawing table was constructed and assembled in conformity with the design. Then, revisions were made for any defect, and the table was reassembled until it was found to be functional and acceptable.

Furthermore, the descriptive-evaluative research design was applied to evaluate the equipment along design and construction of the multi-purpose drafting table. The main data-gathering instrument used was a set of questionnaire checklists supplemented by unstructured interviews and observation.

Source of Data

A total of seventy (70) respondents were included in the study composed of ten (10) industry experts from business firms and schools such as architects, draftsmen, civil engineers, and innovators. Likewise, the twenty (20) Technical Vocational Education (TVE) teachers and forty (40) senior and junior drafting students from the Reina Mercedes Vocational and Industrial School were included as respondents of the study. On the other hand, the purposive sampling technique was used to get the necessary data for the evaluation.

Data Gathering Instruments

The modified instrument taken from Mr. Manuel E. Ruma of Isabela State University Cauayan Campus consisted of the following criteria for evaluating the acceptability of the developed project in terms of *design and construction, functionality, and safety*.

The data needed were gathered through the administered and retrieved questionnaire checklist from the respondents.

Data-Gathering Procedure

Permission to conduct the study was requested from the office of the Principal, Industry Experts, TVE Teachers, and Junior and Senior Drafting students of Reina Mercedes, Vocational and Industrial, School, Reina Mercedes, Isabela.

After permission was granted, administration of the questionnaires followed. Directions about the accomplishment of the questionnaires were done individually. Copies of the questionnaire checklist were retrieved after being accomplished by the respondents.

The survey questionnaire checklist was used to gather information about the acceptability of the Drawing table. And the observation method was also applied to determine the whole structure of the project particularly its acceptability to the users.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

The following statistical tools were used to analyze the data that were gathered.

Weighted Mean (WM). This was used to determine the level of acceptability of this newly developed multi-purpose drafting table in terms of its *design and construction, functionality, comfort, durability safety, and instructional applicability* and to interpret the equivalent meaning of the data gathered.

ANOVA (Analysis Of Variance). This was used to determine the significant differences in the responses and evaluation of the respondents in terms of the identified variables. Meanwhile, the five-point Likert's rating scale as seen in Table below was used to determine the descriptive meaning of the indicators of the variables used.

The collected data were tallied and analyzed using the 5-point scale as shown below:

A. Design and Construction

Weight	Mean Range	Qualitative Description
5	4.20 – 5.00	Very Good
4	3.40 – 4.19	Good
3	2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Good
2	1.80 - 2.59	Sometimes Good
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not at all Good

B. Functionality

Weight	Mean Range	Qualitative Description
5	4.20 – 5.00	Very Functional
4	3.40 – 4.19	Functional
3	2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Functional
2	1.80 - 2.59	Sometimes Functional
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not at all Functional

C. Comfort

Weight	Mean Range	Qualitative Description
5	4.20 – 5.00	Very Comfortable
4	3.40 – 4.19	Comfortable
3	2.60 – 3.39	Sometimes Comfortable
2	1.80 - 2.59	Least Comfortable
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not at all Comfortable

D. Durability

Weight	Mean Range	Qualitative Description
5	4.20 – 5.00	Very Durable
4	3.40 – 4.19	Durable
3	2.60 – 3.39	Fairly Durable
2	1.80 - 2.59	Least Durable
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Durable

E. Safety

Weight	Mean Range	Qualitative Description
5	4.20 – 5.00	Very Safe
4	3.40 – 4.19	Safe
3	2.60 – 3.39	Fairly Safe
2	1.80 - 2.59	Least Safe
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Safe

F. Instructional Applicability

Weight	Mean Range	Qualitative Description
5	4.20 – 5.00	Very Applicable
4	3.40 – 4.19	Applicable
3	2.60 – 3.39	Fairly Applicable
2	1.80 - 2.59	Least Applicable
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Applicable

Activities in the Design and Construction of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table

A. Designing and Layout. The researcher spent some time reading related literature and studies on similar Drafting tables. For the design and layout of the drafting table, the following were taken into consideration:

1. The multi-purpose drafting table should be suited to the students, TVE teachers, and industry expert's level of understanding.
2. It will be constructed using locally and commercially available supplies and materials.
3. It should be manually operated
4. It should have unique and innovative features that make it different from existing drafting tables

B. Construction of the Project. This drafting table was constructed following the procedures below.

1. Prepare and use working drawings (design).
 2. Materials preparation.
 3. From $\frac{3}{4}$ " thick by 4' x 8' marine plywood and 2" x 2" x 14' hardwood, lay out the desired size and cut the different parts of the Drafting Table using a crosscut saw.
 4. Smoothen all straight edges by using a jack plane, with curved edges by the spokeshave.
 5. Sandpaper all parts.
 6. Assemble and nail the frame and different parts of the drafting table using a claw hammer.
 7. Attach the keyboard tray with a drawer slide, a top portion, and the door to the drafting table with the piano hinges using a screwdriver.
 8. Attach the back bar or round bar under the top portion of the drafting table with a clamp lock using a screwdriver.
 9. Polish drafting table with clear gloss lacquer or with paint using an air compressor.
 10. Install all the electrical parts with Cord, PVC wall Molding, safety breaker, Florescent lamp, Snap switch, 4 Gang outlet, electric box fan, and clip table lamp with bulb.
 11. Attach the tempered glass on the top portion of the drafting table.
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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Project Presentation

Figure 1. The Multi-Purpose Drafting Table

Description of the Parts and Functions of the Completed Project

1. **Keyboard tray with drawer slide** keeps the mouse, keyboard for closer touch typing, and art materials for painting. The tray is in line with the elbow and hand-rested for comfortable typing and painting.
2. **The top of the Drafting table** is the adjustable top portion from flat to 80 degrees angle /vertical with main work surface dimensions of 48" x 32".It is used for tracing, cutting, photographic silk screen printing, designing, sketching, mechanical, freehand drawing, reading, writing, and so on. It is a Transparent Tempered Glass.
3. **Adjustable back used** to adjust the inclination of the top portion of the drafting table into flat to 80-degree angles/ vertical. It is a 9mm galvanized iron bar.
4. **Lightings-** used for tracing and photographic silk screen printing and it can be used according to situation and condition. There are two types of lighting, the clip table lamp and the light-emitting-diode fluorescent lamp.
5. **Storage of built-in computer set-** the computer storage is directed to the users, easy to open and close, and well secured. It is used for computer-aided design operation and encoding.
6. **Electric fan** for better ventilation purposes. It is directed to the users.
7. **Padded footrest** to keep the feet flat, slightly under the table.
8. **Build in pencil groove-**serve as a stopper for pencil, triangles, pen, and other drawing tools and materials.
9. **Electrical Part-** with Cord, PVC wall Molding, safety breaker, Florescent lamp, Snap switch, 4 Gang outlet, electric box fan, and clip table lamp with bulb. Used to operate and manipulate the different parts and functions of the drafting table.

10. **Ball Caster**-serve as a table wheel, so that the drafting table is easy to maneuver and transfer.

Uses of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table

1. **Tracing** – Tracing paper and drawing paper (Architectural layout and detail drawing)
2. **Prepare and operate Computer-Aided-Design (CAD)** - Architectural layout and detail
3. **Painting** – using Canvas painting
4. **Photographic silk screen printing or process** – T-shirt Printing
5. **Cutting** – using paper, cardboard, illustration board, styrofoam, and drafting cutter. (Letters cutting and pattern development)
6. **Mechanical Drawing** – isometric, orthographic and other axonometric drawing
7. **Freehand Drawing** – lettering on the title block and another freehand drawing
8. **Office Works**- Writing, reading, and encoding.
9. **Others**- Sketching, blueprint reading, and so on.

Evaluation of the Project

Table 1. Level of Acceptability of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table as Evaluated by Industry Experts, Technical Vocational Education (TVE) Teachers, and Senior and Junior Drafting Students in terms of Design and Construction

A. Design and Construction Indicators	Industry Experts Mean	Q D	TVE-Teachers' Mean	Q D	Seniors & Junior-Students' Mean	Q D
1. The overall look of the design and construction of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table	4.7	VG	4.95	VG	4.9	VG
2. The components and parts of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table	4.8	VG	4.9	VG	4.85	VG
3. The uniqueness of the design and construction of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table	4.6	VG	4.9	VG	4.85	VG
4. The flexibility of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table	4.8	VG	4.8	VG	4.8	VG
5. The electrical components of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table	4.8	VG	4.75	VG	4.88	VG
Overall Weighted Mean	4.74	VG	4.86	VG	4.85	VG

As can be seen in the table above, the computed overall mean of the industry experts is 4.74, 4.86 for the TVE teachers, and 4.85 for the junior and senior drafting

students. On the whole, the three groups of respondents rated the multi-purpose drafting table as “*very good*”. This shows that the overall appearance of the drafting table is attractive. The respondents appreciated how the project was designed and constructed.

In support of the above finding, Ombos (2015) concluded in his study on furniture and cabinet making and fabrication that properly designed and constructed furniture is presentable and good-looking.

Table 2. Level of Acceptability of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table as Evaluated by Industry Experts, Technical Vocational Education (TVE) Teachers, and Senior and Junior Drafting Students in terms of Functionality

B. Functionality Indicators	Industry Experts Mean	Q D	TVE-Teachers Mean	Q D	Junior & Senior - Students Mean	Q D
1. The design of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table is effective as intended for shop plates and exercises.	4.9	VF	4.9	VF	4.9	VF
2. The Multi-Purpose Drafting Table can perform other related activities and operations for students’ use, properly.	4.5	VF	4.85	VF	4.80	VF
3. The overall performance of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table in all its intended use for different activities	4.6	VF	4.65	VF	4.68	VF
4. The developed Multi-Purpose Drafting Table is serving its purpose efficiently and effectively.	4.8	VF	4.85	VF	4.85	VF
5. The different parts of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table are working properly in their specific desired function.	4.9	VF	4.9	VF	4.9	VF
Overall Weighted Mean	4.74	VF	4.83	VF	4.83	VF

As to the level of acceptability of the multi-purpose drafting table, the industry experts gave an overall weighted mean of 4.74. Meanwhile, the TVE teachers and junior and senior drafting students gave the same overall weighted mean of 4.83 respectively. The ratings given by three groups of respondents yielded a qualitative description of “*very functional*”. This shows that the multi-purpose drafting table is very useful and suitable for artwork and other drafting activities.

Meanwhile, Table 4 presents the level of acceptability of the multi-purpose drafting table as evaluated by industry experts, Technical Vocational Education (TVE) teachers, and senior and junior drafting students along comfort.

Table 3. Level of Acceptability of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table as Evaluated by Industry Experts, Technical Vocational Education (TVE) Teachers, and Senior and Junior Drafting Students in terms of Comfort

C. Comfort Indicators	Industry Experts Mean	Q D	TVE-Teachers' Mean	Q D	Junior & Senior - Students Mean	Q D
1. The adjustable keyboard, mouse, and art tray	4.7	VC	4.95	VC	4.68	VC
2. The height of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table	4.5	VC	4.95	VC	4.6	VC
3. The position of the top surface (adjustable from flat to 80 degrees angle/vertical)	4.7	VC	4.8	VC	4.7	VC
4. The work surface is by the paper size	4.7	VC	4.9	VC	4.75	VC
5. The desk lamp and fluorescent tube used as a light table	4.7	VC	4.8	VC	4.8	VC
Overall Weighted Mean	4.66	VC	4.88	VC	4.71	VC

As appearing in Table 3, the acceptability level of the multi-purpose drafting table concerning comfortability gained overall weighted means of 4.88, 4.71, and 4.66 as evaluated by TVE teachers, junior and senior drafting students, and industry experts respectively. Generally, the multi-purpose drafting table was found “*very comfortable*”. This shows that it is very comfortable to use as it is convenient and relaxing.

Table 4 presents the level of acceptability of the multi-purpose Drafting Table as evaluated by the respondents along with durability.

Table 4. Level of Acceptability of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table as Evaluated by Industry Experts, Technical Vocational Education (TVE) Teachers, and Senior and Junior Drafting Students in terms of Durability

D. Durability Indicators	Industry Experts Mean	Q D	TVE-Teachers' Mean	Q D	Junior & Senior - Students Mean	Q D
1. The tempered glass surface of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table	4.6	VD	4.95	VD	4.83	VD

2. The hardwood frame and the parts of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table	4.9	VD	4.85	VD	4.9	VD
3. The various materials used in making Multi-Purpose Drafting Table	4.6	VD	4.95	VD	4.78	VD
4. The storage shelf for the computer set	4.8	VD	4.9	VD	4.85	VD
5. The adjustable back bar of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table	4.8	VD	4.95	VD	4.83	VD
Overall Weighted Mean	4.74	VD	4.92	VD	4.84	VD

The table reflects the acceptability level of the multi-purpose drafting table as to durability. The computed overall weighted mean of 4.92 TVE teachers, 4.84 junior and senior drafting students, and 4.74 industry experts yielded a common description of “very durable”.

This implies that the multi-purpose drafting table is strong and long-lasting. It is resilient due to the hardwood used.

Meanwhile, Table 5 gives the level of acceptability of the multi-purpose drafting table as evaluated by industry experts, Technical Vocational Education (TVE) teachers, and senior and junior Drafting students along with safety.

Table 5. Level of Acceptability of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table as Evaluated by Industry Experts, Technical Vocational Education (TVE) Teachers, and Senior and Junior Drafting Students in terms of Safety

E. Safety Indicators	Industry Experts Mean	Q D	TVE-Teachers Mean	Q D	Junior & Senior - Students Mean	Q D
1. The Multi-Purpose Drafting Table is safe to use and user-friendly	4.9	VS	4.95	VS	4.75	VS
2. The safety condition of the parts and components of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table	4.9	VS	4.9	VS	4.6	VS
3. The installed electrical components of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table	4.8	VS	4.85	VS	4.68	VS
4. The various materials used in making Multi-Purpose Drafting Table	4.8	VS	4.85	VS	4.78	VS
5. The working edge of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table	4.9	VS	4.95	VS	4.65	VS

Overall Weighted Mean	4.86	VS	4.9	VS	4.69	VS
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As indicated in the table, on safety the multi-purpose drafting table got an overall weighted mean of 4.86 from industry experts and 4.9 TVE teachers while it received a mean average of 4.69 from the junior and senior drafting students. Overall, the multi-purpose drafting table was rated as “very safe” to use. This means that the table is safe to use and user-friendly. The major parts and electrical components are properly assembled and safely installed.

Table 6 below presents the level of acceptability of the multi-purpose drafting as regards instructional applicability.

Table 6. Level of Acceptability of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table as Evaluated by Industry Experts, Technical Vocational Education (TVE) Teachers, and Senior and Junior Drafting Students in terms of Instructional Applicability

F. Instructional Applicability Indicators	Industry Experts Mean	Q D	TVE-Teachers' Mean	Q D	Junior & Senior - Students Mean	Q D
1. The Multi-Purpose Drafting Table can be effective for instructional and shop use	4.9	VA	4.95	VA	4.88	VA
2. The use of a Multi-Purpose Drafting Table for letter cutting, pattern development, painting, mechanical and freehand drawing, sketching, silk screen printing, CAD, and other drafting outputs	4.9	VA	4.95	VA	4.85	VA
3. The use of a Multi-Purpose Drafting Table in general as a normal student desk, for reading, writing, blueprint reading, and other related activities	4.8	VA	4.75	VA	4.8	VA
4. The use of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table for better following of teaching instructions	4.8	VA	4.95	VA	4.75	VA
5. The operation and manipulation of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table according to the needed action for each activity	4.9	VA	4.9	VA	4.75	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	4.86	VA	4.9	VA	4.81	VA

As the data indicate, the computed overall weighted means of 4.9, 4.86, and 4.81 from evaluation of industry experts, TVE teachers, and junior and senior drafting students respectively, yielded the corresponding qualitative description "very applicable".

This shows that the multi-purpose drafting table is effective for instructional and shopwork use. The drafting table can be used in teaching the proper method of cutting letters, pattern development, painting, mechanical and freehand drawing, sketching, silk screen printing, CAD, and other drafting outputs.

Comparison in the Evaluation of the Three Groups of Respondents as to the Acceptability of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table

Table 7. Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table in terms of Design and Construction

Source of Variation	df	SS	MS	F_{computed} Value	Critical Value ($\alpha = 5\%$)	Result	Decision
Between Groups	2	0.05	.025	3.33	3.88	Not Significant	Accept the null hypothesis
Within Groups	12	0.09	.0075				
Total	14	.14					

Note: df – Degrees of freedom SS – Sum of squares MS – Mean of squares
 α – Level of Significance Ho – Null hypothesis

Along with design and construction, the F-computed value is 3.33 while the F-critical value is 3.88. At 4 degrees of freedom, the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) exhibited a non-significant result. This implies that there is no significant difference between the evaluations of the three groups of respondents as to the acceptability of the multi-purpose Drafting table along with design and construction. Hence, the null hypothesis is "accepted". This denotes that the three groups of respondents had the same evaluation regarding the design and construction of the multi-purpose drafting table. Furthermore, this is acceptable for them because of its uniqueness, flexibility, design, and construction.

Table 8. Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table in terms of Functionality

Source of Variation	df	SS	MS	F_{computed} Value	Critical Value ($\alpha = 5\%$)	Result	Decision
Between Groups	2	.17	.085	12.69	3.88	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Within Groups	12	.08	.0067				

Total	14	.25					
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As to the functionality of the multi-purpose Drafting table, the F-computed value is 12.69 much greater than the F-critical value of 3.88. At 4 degrees of freedom, the ANOVA gave a significant result. Meaning, there is a significant difference in the evaluations of the respondents on the acceptability of the Drafting table in terms of functionality. In this case, the null hypothesis is “*rejected*.” This implies that the three groups of respondents have different evaluations of the acceptability of its functionality by its purposes, uses, and suitability in their respective activities or works.

Table 9. Analysis of Variance of Respondents’ Evaluations on the Acceptability of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table in Terms of Comfort

Source of Variation	df	SS	MS	F_{computed} Value	Critical Value ($\alpha = 5\%$)	Result	Decision
Between Groups	2	.133	.665	10.73	3.88	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Within Groups	12	.074	.0062				
Total	14	.027					

As to the significant difference between the evaluations of the three groups of respondents on the acceptability of the multi-purpose Drafting table along with comfort, the ANOVA exhibited a significant result. This shows that there is a significant difference between the evaluations of the respondents in terms of acceptability along comfort. Hence, the null hypothesis is “*rejected*”. This indicates that the three groups of the respondents have different views in terms of the acceptability along comfort of the multi-purpose drafting table. Therefore, it implies that some of the respondents preferably want to work comfortably based on their height, position, work surface, and lighting on the drafting table for a long period

Table 10. Analysis of Variance of Respondents’ Evaluations on the Acceptability of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table in terms of Durability

Source of Variation	df	SS	MS	F_{computed} Value	Critical Value ($\alpha = 5\%$)	Result	Decision
Between Groups	2	0.081	.0405	6.43	3.88	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Within Groups	12	0.076	0.0063				
Total	14	.157					

As seen in the Table, the F-computed value of 6.43 is much greater than the F-critical value of 3.88. At 4 degrees of freedom, the ANOVA exhibited a significant result.

This goes to show that there is a significant difference between the evaluations of the respondents on the acceptability of the multi-purpose Drafting table along with its durability. In this case, the null hypothesis is “*rejected*”. Thus, the respondents would like to ensure the quality of the drafting table like the storage shelf and various materials so that it will become more useful over a long period.

Table 11. Analysis of Variance of Respondents’ Evaluations on the Acceptability of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table in terms of Safety

Source of Variation	df	SS	MS	F_{computed} Value	Critical Value ($\alpha = 5\%$)	Result	Decision
Between Groups	2	.14432	.07216	9.05	3.88	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Within Groups	12	.09568	.00797				
Total	14	.24					

As to the significant difference between the evaluations of the three groups of respondents on the acceptability of the multi-purpose Drafting table along safety, the F-computed value is 9.05 while the F-critical value is 3.88 at a .05 level of significance. Since the F-computed value is much greater than the tabular value, the ANOVA exhibited a significant result. This shows that there is a significant difference between the evaluations of the respondents in terms of acceptability along safety. Hence, the null hypothesis is “*rejected*”. This implies that the respondents have different evaluations in terms of the acceptability along safety of the drafting table. Consequently, this shows that the table should be safer in terms of the safety condition of the parts and installed electrical components.

Table 12. Analysis of Variance of Respondents’ Evaluations on the Acceptability of the Multi-Purpose Drafting Table in terms of Instructional Applicability

Source of Variation	Df	SS	MS	F_{computed} Value	Critical Value ($\alpha = 5\%$)	Result	Decision
Between Groups	2	.02	.01	3.03	3.88	Not Significant	Accept the Null Hypothesis
Within Groups	12	.04	.0033				
Total	14	.24					

Along with instructional applicability, the F-computed value is 3.03 while the F-critical value is 3.88. At 4 degrees of freedom, the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) exhibited a non-significant result. This means that there is no significant difference between the evaluations of the three groups of

respondents as to the acceptability of the multi-purpose Drafting table along with instructional applicability. Hence, the null hypothesis is “*accepted*”.

This implies that the respondents have the same satisfaction in terms of the functionality of the drafting table that could help them in working with their different tasks or activities, especially in effective instructional purposes like painting, letter cutting, pattern development, mechanical and freehand drawing, sketching, silk screen printing and computer-aided design operation and other.

Suggested Improvement Checklist of the Multi-purpose Drafting Table Parts

The following tables present the suggested improvement checklist of the different parts and components of the designed and constructed multi-purpose drafting table.

Table 15 below shows the suggestions of the respondents as to the keyboard of the multi-purpose drafting table.

Table 13. Suggested Improvement Checklist of the Keyboard of the Drafting Table

Indicators	Industry Experts			Teachers			Students			Total		
	F	%	R	F	%	R	F	%	R	F	%	R
1. The keyboard tray should have a hand-rest for comfortable typing	7	70.00	1	5	25.00	1	22	55.00	1	34	48.57	1
2. Size	3	30.00	2	5	25.00	1	11	27.50	3	19	27.14	2
3. The keyboard tray should be closer	1	10.00	3	0	0.00	3	13	32.50	2	14	20.00	3
4. The keyboard tray should be farther	0	0.00	4	1	5.00	2	2	5.00	5	3	4.29	4
5. The keyboard tray should be in line	0	0.00	4	0	0.00	3	3	7.50	4	3	4.29	4

with the elbow											
Total	10	100.00		20	100.00		40	100.00		70	100.00

As seen in the Table, 48.57% of the respondents suggested that the “*Keyboard tray should have a handrest for comfortable typing.*” The respondents have rated this item as the highest having 70% from industry experts, 25% from teachers, and 55 % from students. This denotes that most respondents preferred to work with a comfortable place to rest their wrists while typing on the keyboard to avoid exhaustion.

Meanwhile, Table 16 presents the suggestions of the respondents at the top of the drafting table.

Table 14. Suggested Improvement Checklist at the Top of the Drafting Table

Indicators	Industry Experts			Teachers			Students			Total		
	F	%	R	F	%	R	F	%	R	F	%	R
1. Surface area should be wider	1	10.00	4	3	15.00	1	12	30.00	1	16	22.86	1
2. Change the surface for better maintenance of the top	2	20.00	2	2	10.00	2	10	25.00	2	14	20.00	2
3. The size of the top should fit the size of the paper	3	30.00	1	0	0.00	4	5	12.50	3	8	11.43	3
4. Adjust the Inclination of the top	2	20.00	3	1	5.00	3	4	10.00	4	7	10.00	4
5. Construction material of the top	1	10.00	4	0	0.00	5	3	7.50	5	4	5.71	5
Total	10	100.00		20	100.00		40	100.00		70	100.00	

Based on the above data, 22.86% or a majority of the respondents recommended that the “*surface area of the table be wider.*” This was based on the response of 15% from the teachers, 30% from the students, and 10% from the industry experts.

Moreover, 20% of industry experts, 10% of teachers, and 25% of students having a total of 20% suggested the “*change surface for better maintenance of the top.*”

This implies that the respondents preferred to work in a wider space for a spacious working area and recommended changing the surface of the top to avoid any markings, scratches, and scattered paints that could stain or damage the top of the table.

Table 15 indicates the suggestions of the respondents as to the adjustable back bar of the drafting table.

Table 15. Suggested Improvement Checklist of the Adjustable Back Bar of the Drafting Table

Indicators	Industry Experts			Teachers			Students			Total		
	F	%	R	F	%	R	F	%	R	F	%	R
1. Rotational adjustment	6	60.00	1	2	10.00	2	20	50.00	1	28	40.00	1
2. Stainless round bar	2	20.00	2	4	20.00	1	8	20.00	2	14	20.00	2
3. Bigger size of round bar	1	10.00	3	1	5.00	3	4	10.00	3	6	8.57	3
4. Smaller size of round bar	0	0.00	4	1	5.00	3	1	2.50	4	2	2.86	4
5. Galvanize Iron round bar	0	0.00	4	0	0.00	4	1	2.50	4	1	1.43	5
Total	10	100.00		20	100.00		40	100.00		70	100.00	

The adjustable back bar should be in a “*rotational adjustment*” as suggested by 60% of the Industry Experts, 50% of the students, and 10% of the teachers. This item was ranked as number one (1) or 40% of the respondents. On the other hand, 20% of the total respondents or the item that was ranked as number two (2) was the back bar should be “*made of the stainless round bar*” as suggested by 20 % of the industry experts, 20 % of teachers and 20% of the students.

This denotes that the majority of the respondents preferred that the adjustable back bar be in a rotational adjustment so that the user will easily adjust the top of the table when needed. Furthermore, it should be made of a stainless round bar for the assurance of its durability and non-rust.

Table 16 presents suggestions of the respondents as to the dimensions of the drafting table.

Table 16. Suggested Improvement Checklist of the Dimensions of the Drafting Table

Indicators	Industry Experts			Teachers			Students			Total		
	F	%	R	F	%	R	F	%	R	F	%	R
1. The table should be wider	3	30.00	1	4	20.00	1	9	22.50	2	16	22.86	1
2. The table should be lower	3	30.00	2	1	5.00	2	10	25.00	1	14	20.00	2
3. The table should be higher	0	0.00	3	0	0.00	4	8	20.00	3	8	11.43	3
4. The table should be longer	0	0.00	4	1	5.00	3	2	5.00	4	3	4.29	4
5. The table should be shorter	0	0.00	5	0	0.00	4	1	2.50	5	1	1.43	5
Total	10	100.00		20	100.00		40	100.00		70	100.00	

As shown in the table, 30% of the industry experts, 20 % of the teachers, and 22.5 % of the students, having a total of 22.86% of the respondents have proposed that the dimensions of the table should be “wider”. Similarly, 30% of the industry experts, 5% of the teachers, and 25 % of the students having a total of 20% have recommended that it should be “lower”.

This implies that the respondents are more comfortable working with a wider top dimension of the table for them to spread out the other materials that they need while working on the table as well as for their convenience. Moreover, it should be lower to provide versatility and ease of use for the respondents.

The suggestions of the respondents to improve the brightness of lighting for tracing and photographic silk screen printing are presented in Table 17.

Table 17. Suggested Improvement Checklist of the Brightness of Lighting for Tracing and Photographic Silk Screen Printing

Indicators	Industry Experts			Teachers			Students			Total		
	F	%	R	F	%	R	F	%	R	F	%	R
1. Lights' brightness should be adjustable	5	50.00	1	11	55.00	1	23	57.50	1	39	55.71	1
2. Lights should be brighter	1	10.00	3	3	15.00	2	6	15.00	2	10	14.29	2

3. Lights should be dimmer	2	20.00	2	0	0.00	5	5	12.50	3	7	10.00	3
4. Lights should be light-emitting-diode for user-friendliness	1	10.00	3	2	10.00	3	4	10.00	4	7	10.00	3
5. Lights should be light-emitting-diode for economic purposes	1	10.00	3	1	5.00	4	4	10.00	5	6	8.57	4
Total	10	100.00		20	100.00		40	100.00		70	100.00	

As shown in the table, 50% of Industry experts, 55% of teachers, and 57.5% of students having a total of 55.71% have suggested that the “*brightness of the light should be adjustable*”. This implies that the user can easily adjust the lighting once he needs a brighter or dimmer light during his/her work on the table. Furthermore, 10% of industry experts, 15% each from the teachers and students with a total of 14.29% proposed that the “*lights should be brighter.*” This denotes that some of the respondents preferred to work with brighter lights in favor of photographic silk screen printing. This could be in some instances that the mesh screen is then coated with a layer of light-reactive emulsion, which will harden when developed under bright light.

Table 18 presents the suggested improvement checklist for the storage built-in computer set of the drafting table.

Table 18. Suggested Improvement Checklist of the Storage of built-in computer set

Indicators	Industry Experts			Teachers			Students			Total		
	F	%	R	F	%	R	F	%	R	F	%	R
1. Well-secured		60.00	1	3	15.00	2	15	37.50	1	24	34.29	1
2. The computer storage should be directed to the users	2	20.00	2	4	20.00	1	12	30.00	2	18	25.71	2

3. The computer storage should be bigger	2	20.00	2	3	15.00	2	7	17.50	4	12	17.14	3
4. Easy to open and close	1	10.00	3	1	5.00	3	9	22.50	3	11	15.71	4
5. The computer storage should be smaller	0	0.00	4	0	0.00	4	3	7.50	5	3	4.29	5
Total	10	100.00		20	100.00		40	100.00		70	100.00	

As seen in the Table, industry experts (60 %), teachers (15 %), and students (37.5%) with a total of 34.29 % suggested that the built-in computer set should “*be secured with lockers*”. This denotes that the computer set must be secured for the safety of the files being saved at the computer and safety storage. Furthermore, The “*computer storage should be directed to the users*” as suggested by 20% of industry partners, 20% of teachers, and 30% of students. This implies easy or direct access to the eyes of the users and proper posture through their work on the computer.

Finally, Table 19 gives the suggested improvement checklist from the respondents as to the ventilation of the multi-purpose drafting table.

Table 19. Suggested Improvement Checklist of the Ventilation

Indicators	Industry Experts			Teachers			Students			Total		
	F	%	R	F	%	R	F	%	R	F	%	R
1. The size of the installed electrical fan should be bigger or should have better ventilation	3	30.00	1	3	15.00	1	19	47.50	1	25	35.71	1
2. Installation of the electric fan should be directed to the user	1	10.00	2	0	0.00	3	9	22.50	2	10	14.29	2
3. Installation of electric fan.	1	10.00	2	3	15.00	1	6	15.00	3	10	14.29	2
4. Location of the electric fan on the table	3	30.00	1	1	5.00	2	5	12.50	4	9	12.86	3
Total	10	100.00		20	100.00		40	100.00		70	100.00	

As shown in the table, 30% of the industry experts, 15% of teachers, and 47.5% of students having a total of 35.71% of the respondents suggested that the *“installed fan should be bigger for better ventilation.”* This denotes that the respondents feel more comfortable working with better ventilation.

Conclusions

The creation of the Multi-purpose Drafting Table is made possible through a process. Its design and layout are in accordance with its usefulness and suitability for drafting students, TVE teachers, and industry experts. Local hardwood materials like *Red Lawan* and highly polished marine plywood which are used in making the drafting table are readily available in the market. Based on respondents' testing and evaluation, the multi-purpose drafting table is useful, user-friendly, strong, long-lasting, safe to use, and effective in Drafting Technology instructional activities. Generally, it is a highly accepted project.

Evaluations of the three groups of respondents on the acceptability of the multi-purpose drafting table vary along with functionality, comfort, durability, and safety due to their different perceptions, degrees of specialization, and areas of concern. However, the respondents' common evaluation of the acceptability of the drafting table along with instructional applicability, design, and construction is explained by their satisfaction with the features of the drafting table and its usefulness for instructional purposes. Finally, the respondents' suggestions for some improvements are based on the different parts and components of the developed multi-purpose drafting table.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. More features should be incorporated into the Multi-purpose Drafting Table to be more useful.
2. High-quality materials should be used for the different parts of the table to make it more durable and lasting.
3. More unique and innovative features, design, and layout of the drafting table be done to make the product different from existing other projects.
4. The drafting table should perform other related activities and functions.
5. The height of the drafting table should be adjustable for the user's comfort.
6. The drafting table should be proposed to the school for mass production and income.
7. The electrical parts of the drafting table should be safely and properly installed.
8. The design and functions of the drafting table should be in a wider scope to become more equally functional to the users.
9. The keyboard tray should have a hand-test for comfortable typing.
10. The dimensions of the Drafting Table be wider for a spacious working area.

11. The adjustable back bar should be in rotational adjustment for easy manipulation of the table when it is needed.
12. The light's brightness should be adjustable for other activities.
13. The computer storage should be secured with lockers for the security of the files.
14. The size of the installed electric fan should be bigger for better ventilation.
15. A similar study should be conducted to increase the number of instructional materials in technological areas.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

As the author of this study, I declare my adherence to ethical standards. Informed consent was obtained, and respondents could withdraw at any time. Anonymity was maintained, and their well-being was safeguarded. There were no conflicts of interest, and plagiarism was strictly avoided. I ensured an unbiased interpretation of the findings, and the results were intended solely for research purposes.

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